

Emerging Changes and Trends in IT Industry

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Abstract:

Employability is on the decline in most areas and employers are being faced with the issues of finding people with adequate soft skills. There have been various measures adopted to improve soft skills in employees, even after the employees have been absorbed by the employers companies are looking at avenues to increase soft skills and build capabilities in employment. Certain practices that are prevalent widely in the IT industry in terms of options of work from home, and elimination of strict office hours have seen a decline as employers realize that this added to enhanced productivity by human interface in physical environments. This paper is an exploratory study of a few companies in the information technology industry and some such trends in the IT industry that contributes to improved effectiveness of employees and enhances skill sets availability.

Keywords: employability, skill sets, productivity

1. Introduction

Employability is not just understood in terms of getting a job, but possessing the skills and capabilities that allow you to be employed. Definitions and models of graduate employability abound: it has been variously described as a graduate's potential to obtain employment, accompanied by a set of achievements, understandings and personal attributes (Yorke 2004) and a blend of understanding, skilful practices, efficacy beliefs and reflectiveness (Little 2006). It has further been described as the 'capability' of becoming an effective operator in the world (whether in an employment or other social setting); that is, to have the confidence to take effective and appropriate action, live and work effectively with others, and continue to learn from experiences, as individuals and with others, in a diverse and changing society.

The International Labour Organisation (ILO), in a report, has projected unemployment in India at 18.6 million for 2018, higher than the 18.3 million in 2017. The World Bank (WB), in a report, has warned India -- a nation of 1.32 billion people must create 8.1 million jobs a year to maintain its employment rate. Predictions regarding India's job market are a little discomfoting. Educational institutions need to revamp and revisit how universities prepare youngsters for the future, the existing talent crunch would only worsen, and with the major issue countries like India would face in the backdrop of an ever growing pool of job seekers.

Employability rose to 14 per centage points in the last five years, according to India Skills Report. Around 57 per cent of the final year engineering graduates were found to be employable, an increase of about five percentage points since the previous year. The employability among MBA graduates, however had dropped by three percentage points over the previous year the report added that with the exponential increase in the number of MBA colleges, the quality of talent seems to be declining. The report also found that there was a drop in employability of B. Pharma graduates.

Today, in employment situation, demand for skills and capabilities prevails over basic qualifications, employers are focused on the skilled workforce and hence students likewise need to focus on learning courses which are a combination of both- theoretical knowledge and practical applicability.

2. Employability Indicators

Employability in India: Talent crunch across industry forces stakeholders to point fingers at a spiritless education system. "Accessing the right talent, placing the right talent at the right time is a challenge many Indian businesses face," management consultancy AT Kearney's MD and country head, Vikas Kaushal, said in an interview to the Mint. But, by 2019, IT technical specialist hires will fall by more than five percent. By 2021, 40 percent of all IT staff will hold multiple roles, most of which will be business-related rather than technology-related, according to Gartner. The research firm also predicts that by 2020, 75 percent of all organisations will experience visible business disruptions owing to infrastructure and operational (I&O) skill gaps, a huge increase from 20 percent in 2016.

A talent crunch across sectors is said to be the reason behind employment opportunities drying up even when there are vacancies. The education system needs to do its bit to help students future-proof their employability levels, said stakeholders.

The curriculum has not kept pace with the rapidly changing times and therefore vacancies can be hard to fill, said Kris Lakshmikanth, Founder Chairman and MD of The Head Hunters India. Employability will improve when the syllabus reflects the demands of the industry. "Educational institutes churn out graduates who lack skills required to work on-site. If you were to deploy a chemical engineer to a plant, he/she won't know what to do as the recruit does not have that training."

The ALTC Competitive Grant, Building course team capacity to enhance graduate employability, is collaboration between Curtin University of Technology, University of Southern Queensland, RMIT University and Victoria University. The aim of this project is to investigate ways to build the capacity of teaching staff so as to identify, model and assess graduate employability skills. This project of ALTC Competitive Grant, has three principal outcomes: (1) here they create the Graduate Employability Indicators, surveys which gather the perceptions of graduates, employers and course teaching teams in relation to the teaching, assessment, achievement and importance of employability skills in specific courses; (2) resources for university teaching staff to enhance strengths and address gaps in their confidence to teach and assess those skills; and (3) a process for using the indicators and resources to participate in benchmarking partnerships with other universities.

The major employability indicators as identified by this study are as follows –

1. Work Related knowledge

2. Writing
3. Speaking
4. Thinking Critically
5. Quantitative problems
6. Using ICT
7. Working with others
8. Learning Independently
9. Racial/ethnic understanding
10. Solving Problems
11. Values and ethics
12. Welfare of community
13. Industry Awareness
14. Social Contexts

Many graduates responded that the best aspects of the course were related to capability development in communication, discipline knowledge, teamwork skills, critical thinking and problem-solving. Areas identified as needing improvement were related to general industry awareness. Graduates commented that the course could be improved with more work experience, practical examples and linking the assessments to real-world problems rather than theory. Graduates also commented that employers use a wider-range of software programs and other technologies than are taught to students, stating that more instruction on some programs and the introduction of other software packages used in industry would be an improvement to the course.

3. Academic Responsibility

It is then the responsibility of the academic institutions to ensure that the right level of employability garnering content is input into curriculum of the courses. The practicality aspects of learning independently, thinking critically, and working with others can be inculcated by creating group activities, practical exercises, role plays and so on. Many universities have also placed a thrust on research oriented learning by including research as topic of study. Students are given tasks to write research papers and make an analytical study

of the research topic. This ensures that students develop independent thinking capability and analytical mindsets. It is also important to incorporate value sand ethics and welfare of the community by driving down concepts of corporate social responsibility, community welfare activities in the extra curricular activities.

4. Conclusion

With concerted efforts, the temples of education- colleges and universities and students on their part can ensure that the employability gaps are bridged as much as possible. Ensuring the turnout of graduates are industry ready and possessing the right skills and capabilities is essential. We have a long way to go and the entire ecosystem should focus on bridging the talent pool, ensuring that right from the school level up to the professional level should be focused on learning.

5. References

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